

JOPHIL: Re-orienting the foundations of 'New Science': John Philoponus and the modern theories of space and void (1520-1604)

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Abstract	The Deliverable D2.1, Census of manuscripts and printed editions of Philoponus' <i>Physics</i> , provides a list of all know manuscripts and printed editions transmitting the work (both in Greek and in Latin). The census offers a window onto the material reception of Philoponus' work and maps the actual availability of the text in the context of late medieval and early modern Europe.
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¹ The labels used mean: Public — fully open (automatically posted online); Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; EU classified —RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL, SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET under Decision 2015/444

The census consists of two parts. Part 1 supplies a list of manuscripts witnesses of the text. No Latin manuscripts seem to have survived, but only codices transmitting the Greek text. Part 2 offers a list of all printed editions of the work, starting from the edition of the Greek text, followed by the nine editions of the Latin translation of the work, with name of the translator next to each of them. The CNCE number is provided, so as to enable users to easily retrieve the item on the Edit16 database.

GREEK MANUSCRIPTS OF PHILOPONUS' PHYSICS

	COUNTRY	CITY	LIBRARY	SHELFMARK K	FOLIOS	CENTURY	VIT*	NOTES
1	Vatican City	Vatican City	BAV	Barb. gr. 591	1r-16v	12 (2/2)		Frgs from books 2-3
2	Vatican City	Vatican City	BAV	Ott. gr. 32	17r-27r	16	V	Sirtleto. Frags book 8
3	Vatican City	Vatican City	BAV	Vat. gr. 250	1r-342v	15	N	Bks 1-4. Poor. Pope Nicholas V. Agrees with K
4	Vatican City	Vatican City	BAV	Vat. gr. 1028	93r-370v	15	L	Bks 1-4. Bk 4 copied from G. Only Bks 1-2 good
5	Italy	Florence	BLaur.	Plut. 85.01	648v-650r	13 (4/4)	O	Frgs from F. J. Lascaris. Crete to Florence 1492.
6	Italy	Florence	BLaur.	Plut. 87.06	1r-326r	11	G	Bk 4. N. Niccoli & C. Buondelmonti
7	Italy	Florence	BLaur.	Plut. 87.10	7v	14	D	Frgs from prologue. Agrees with L
8	Italy	Modena	Estense	α. W.3.20 (207)	65r-217r	16		Frgs bks 5-8. Ambrogio Leone da Nola. 1522
9	Italy	Naples	BN V. E. III	III.E.1	1r-255r	14 med.	B	Scholia on Bk 8. Agrees with E and F. G. Onorio
10	Italy	Venice	BNM	gr. IV.20	1r-127r	15 med.		Bk 4 only. G. Argyropoulos. From G
11	Italy	Venice	BNM	gr. Z.194	429r-435v	13 (3/4)		Excerpts from 8.6. Bessarion. Agrees with F
12	Italy	Venice	BNM	gr. Z.219	340r-355r	15 (3/4)	T	Frgs Bk 8. from F. 1465-81 Bessarion
13	Italy	Venice	BNM	gr. Z.220	4r-231v	15 med.	K	Bks 1-4, lacunose. 1435-50 Pletho's circle Mystras
14	Italy	Venice	BNM	gr. Z.227	431r-436r	13 (3/4)	F	Scholia on Bk 8.6. 1450-55 Bessarion
15	Italy	Venice	BNM	gr. Z.230	1r-170v	14 in.	M	Bks 1-4 (4 poor) Gk ed. 1-3. Bessarion, N.L. Tomeo
16	France	Paris	BNF	Coislin 166	1r-109r	14	A	Parts of prologue only. Pierre Séguier (1588-1672)
17	France	Paris	BNF	Grec 1853	3r-67r	9 ex./10 in.	E	Scholia (no 4&7). Late 15 c. for Libreria Medicea
18	France	Paris	BNF	Grec 1859	1r-98r	13	S	Frgs from 8.6 (F). G. Pellitier Venice 1539-42
19	France	Paris	BNF	Grec 2057	1r-235v	14 in.	P	Bks 3-4; inc. mut. From M. N. Ridolff (b. 1501)
20	France	Paris	BNF	Grec 2063	56r-58v	14	R	Scholia Bks 1-3. J. Lascaris (b. 1445)
21	Austria	Wien	ÖNB	phil. gr. 170	23v-25v	15 (2/2)		Frgs from II.2. Johannes Sambucus (b. 1531)

* This refers to the sigla adopted by Girolamo Vitelli in his critical edition of the Greek text (*In Aristotelis Physicorum libros commentaria*, ed. by G. Vitelli, 2 vols, Berlin, Reimer, 1887-1888). Manuscripts without a sigla were not considered by Vitelli.

PRINTED EDITIONS OF PHILOPONUS' COMMENTARY

1535	Venice: Bartolomeo Zanetti	Greek text	CNCE 47896
1539	Venice: Ottaviano Scoto	G. Doroteo	CNCE 31383
1542	Venice: Brandino e Ottaviano Scoto ²	G. Doroteo	CNCE 31407
1546	Venice: Ottaviano Scoto	G. Doroteo	CNCE 33530
1550	Venice: Ottaviano Scoto	G. Doroteo	CNCE 33540
1554	Venice: Ottaviano Scoto	G. Doroteo	CNCE 33545
1558	Venice: Girolamo Scoto	G.B. Rasario	CNCE 32097
1559	Venice: Girolamo Scoto	G.B. Rasario	CNCE 32112
1569	Venice: Vincenzo Valgrisi	G.B. Rasario	CNCE 39015
1581	Venice: Girolamo Scoto	G.B. Rasario	CNCE 32518

² Schmitt, Charles B. 1987. 'Philoponus' Commentary on Aristotle's *Physics* in the Sixteenth Century', in Richard Sorabji (ed.), *Philoponus and the Rejection of Aristotelian Science*, 210-230, London: Duckworth, does not identify the printer (p. 229).